

Sentimental Analysis on Parent's Review Using Naive Bayes Algorithm

Devika Sahadevan
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
devikasahadevan2023a@mca.ajce.in

Sona Maria Sebastian
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
sonasebastian@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Sentimental analysis is technique used to determine whether text data is positive, negative or neutral. Sentimental analysis, also known as opinion mining, is the systematic identification, extraction, quantification, and analysis of affective states and subjective data, using natural language processing and text analysis is typically applied to customer feedback about daycare center. Sentiment analysis is frequently used in marketing, customer service, clinical medicine, and healthcare materials. The proposed system understands the opinions and utilities of parents towards daycare services, and to use this information to improve the quality of care and customer satisfaction. When you read customers feedback you can understand that whether the customer is happy, unhappy. You'll also be able to understand why they're feeling the way they are.

Keywords: Sentiment analysis, Logistic Regression, Data Visualization, Naivebayes, Natural Language Processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the needs and expectations of parents and babysitters in daycare management can be facilitated through the use of customer feedback, which is a valuable tool. Daycare centers can improve the quality of care they provide by analyzing customer feedback and making data-driven decisions. This seminar will explore the use of sentiment analysis in daycare management for customer feedback. To gain insights into the strengths and weaknesses of daycare services and identify areas for improvement, analyzing customer feedback is the objective. The challenges involved in analyzing customer feedback in the context of daycare management, such as dealing with unstructured data, ensuring data privacy, and interpreting sentiment in the context of daycare services, will be discussed. The seminar aims to provide an overview of sentiment analysis and its application in the context of customer feedback in daycare management. Additionally, various techniques and tools used in sentiment analysis, such as natural language processing, machine learning algorithms, and data visualization, will be explored. Daycare centers can improve the quality of care they provide and gain valuable insights into customer satisfaction by utilizing data analytics and machine learning, as demonstrated by the project.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Antony et. al.[1] this study shows a customer feedback review on a product utilizing opinion mining, text mining, and sentiments, which have been affected by changing their opinion on a specific product. This delivers you with a sentimental analysis of numerous smartphone opinions separating them into Positive, Negative, and Neutral Behaviour.

Esha et. al.[2] this paper deliberates how to apply a Support Vector Machine (SVM) machine learning algorithm to classify sentiments for product reviews that analyses different datasets to measure the polarity of reviews whether positive or negative and resulting models are tested to measure the accuracy of SVM algorithm.

Lin et. al.[3] this paper is based on some features, a number of comparative tests using classification algorithms, feature representations, and review length have been conducted. We performed a statistical analysis after crawling an enormous amount of real data and discovered that mobile application reviews share the following four traits: Power-law distribution, short average length, a wide range of lengths, and a substantial polarity difference.

According to K. Lee [4], mining local knowledge can aid in disease eradication. The most prevalent illness that is observed is allergy. The likelihood of developing chronic illness and illness is increasing.

Anant et. al.[5] this paper has covered many standardization techniques for NLP, including their significance and implementation in Python using the NLTK package. A comparison of Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes models is also discussed and implemented. Resulting in the Logistic Regression being more accurate than Naive Bayes.

III. NAIVE BAYES ALGORITHM

Naive Bayes is a supervised learning algorithm built on the bayes theorem and frequently used for classification task. NB is a generative classifier, based on the input given it will classify to the predefined classes. I have used NB because it is the simplest algorithms and can be trained on small dataset

so computation is fast. Bayes theorem is used for decision making and future predictions. Bayes theorem is defines as:

$$P(Y|X) = [P(X|Y) * P(Y)] / P(X)$$

where:

$P(Y|X_i)$: is the conditional probability/ posterior probability that event Y occurs, if X has occurred.

$P(X)$ and $P(Y)$: probability of X and Y independent of each other.

$P(X|Y)$: the conditional probability that event X occurs, given that Y has occurred.

IV. METHODOLOGY

1. DATA COLLECTION:

In this first stage, the data that is entered by the user as feedback, which is the review data are collected from the database for further procedures that are to be done.

2. DATA PRE-PROCESSING:

In sentimental analysis the output is based on the different pre-processing techniques which are applied. Here by using TextBlob, text is cleaned and preprocessed to remove noise, stop words, punctuations, and other irrelevant information.

3. FEATURE EXTRACTION:

After the pre-processing of data the relevant features, such as words or n-grams, are extracted from the text and thereby create a feature set.

4. SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS:

The pre-processed and feature-extracted data is used to train a Naïve Bayes Classifier. This involves calculating the probability of each feature and classify in to the positive, negative or neutral classes.

Finally, the aspect score is calculated. This is done by using the polarity_scores, a module within the TextBlob package of the TextBlob tool.

V. FIGURES AND TABLES

Import the package that are necessary.

```
from textblob import TextBlob
```

Taking reviews (data) form database and using TextBlob find the sentiment polarity.

```
from flask import Flask, request
from textblob import TextBlob
app = Flask(__name__)

@app.route('/sentiment',
methods=['POST'])
def sentiment_analysis():
    texts = request.json.get('texts')
    sentiment_scores = []
    for text in texts:
```

```
blob = TextBlob(text)
sentiment =
blob.sentiment.polarity

sentiment_scores.append(sentiment)
average_sentiment =
sum(sentiment_scores) /
len(sentiment_scores)
response = {
    'positive': len([s for s in
sentiment_scores if s > 0]),
    'negative': len([s for s in
sentiment_scores if s < 0]),
    'neutral': len([s for s in
sentiment_scores if s == 0]),
    'average sentiment':
average_sentiment
}
return response

if __name__ == "__main__":
    app.run()
```

TABLE I:

Feedback Id	User	Feedback	Feedback Date	View
9	pooja@gmail.com	The teachers are amazing, informative and loving.	23-05-01	Review
10	pooja@gmail.com	Its good!	23-05-01	Review
7	alan@gmail.com	I was really disappointed with this daycare.	23-05-01	Review
8	pooja@gmail.com	I have mixed feelings about this daycare	23-05-01	Review

Fig:1

VI. RESULT

Graph related to sentiment polarity find from review.

Fig: 2

Fig:3

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper we proposed sentiment analysis of parents' feedback in daycare using machine learning techniques. We used the TextBlob package, a pre-trained model based on the Naive Bayes technique, to pre-process the feedback dataset and classify the feedback into positive and negative attitudes. The results showed that our method is effective in analyzing parents' feedback and can provide useful insights for daycare management. This approach can be used by daycare centers to improve their services and enhance customer satisfaction. Future work could involve the integration of more advanced machine learning techniques to improve the accuracy of sentiment analysis and expand the scope of the analysis to include other aspects of feedback, such as suggestions for improvement.

VIII. REFERENCES

- 1] Antony Samuels, John Mcgonical, "Sentiment Analysis on Customer Responses", University of Southern California, Caltech, 5 Jul 2020
- 2] Esha Tyagi and Arvind Kumar Sharma, "Sentiment Analysis of Product Reviews using Support Vector Machine Learning Alogithm", Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Vol 10(35), September 2017.
- 3] C. D. Manning, M. Surdeanu, J. Bauer, J. R. Finkel, S. Bethard, and D. McClosky. The stanford corenlp natural language processing toolkit. In ACL (System Demonstrations), pages 55–60, 2014.
- 4] K. Lee, A. Agrawal, and A. N. Choudhary. Mining social media streams to improve public health allergy surveillance. In ASOAM, pages 815– 822, 2015.
- 5] Anant Mahajan, Anshuman Ray, Ashish Verma, Shreya Kohad, Prasheel N Thak are, "Sentiment Analysis using Supervised Machine Learning", International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education, Vol-6 Issue-6 2020